

Synthesis of Bisthiazolo[3,4-b ; 3',2'-d]-1,2,4-triazol-8(3H, 7H)ones as Potential Herbicides

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Cyclodehydration of 2-(4-oxothiazolidin-3-ylamino)- Δ^2 -thiazolin-4-ones (3) with conc. H_2SO_4 furnished bisthiazolo[3,4-b ; 3',2'-d]-1,2,4-triazol-8(3H, 7H)-ones (4). The compounds 3 were prepared by condensation and addition-condensation of thiosemicarbazones (1) with α -haloalkanoic acids and mercaptoacetic acid, respectively. The compounds 3 and 4 were compared with 2,4-D for their herbicidal activity against *C. rotundus* and *C. dactylon*. Based on the screening data, a possible structure-activity relationship has been deduced.

3-AMINO-1,2,4-TRIAZOLE (Amitrole) is a commercial herbicide. Some nitrogen-bridged heterocyclic systems incorporating 1,2,4-triazole nucleus have been reported to display potential herbicidal activity¹⁻⁴. Likewise, 4-thiazolidinone⁵⁻⁸ and Δ^2 -thiazoline⁹⁻¹² derivatives are associated with a broad spectrum pesticidal activity. In view of these reports, we have fused the biolabile 4-thiazolidinone and Δ^2 -thiazoline nuclei with 1,2,4-triazole ring to afford a new tri-cyclic nitrogen-bridged heterocyclic system which might have enhanced herbicidal activity.

The sequence of reactions leading to the formation of the title compounds 4 (Table 1) is depicted in Scheme 1. The condensation of thiosemicarba-

zones (1) with α -haloalkanoic acids furnished 4-thiazolidinones (2) which on addition-condensation with mercaptoacetic acid yielded 2-(4-oxothiazolidin-3-ylamino)- Δ^2 -thiazolin-4-ones (3). The compounds 3 underwent clear cyclodehydration with conc. H_2SO_4 to furnish 4. The compounds 3 were also accessible *via* an alternative route which involves addition-condensation of mercaptoacetic acid followed by the condensation of α -haloalkanoic acids with 2'.

The compounds were characterised by their nmr, ir spectra and elemental analyses. The ir spectra of 3 exhibited significant bands around 1625 (C=N), 1700 (C=O) and 3300 cm^{-1} (NH). The absence of ν NH bond in the ir spectra of 4 was compatible with its assigned structure.

The nmr spectrum of the compound 4b in DMSO- d_6 (at 60 MHz) reveal δ 2.1-2.5 (Ar, 5H, complex m) and 6.0-6.3 (-CH₂-, q).

Experimental

M.ps. reported are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer.

Aldehyde 4-oxo- Δ^2 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones (2a-j): These were prepared by following the method of Rout and Mahapatra¹⁶. An equimolar mixture of an aldehyde thiosemicarbazone (1), α -haloalkanoic acid and anhydrous sodium acetate in ethanol was refluxed for 4 h. Alcohol was distilled off and the residue washed with hot water and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The following compounds 2 were prepared in 75-90% yield. 2a (R = n-C₈H₇; R' = H), m.p. 285-287° (Found: N, 22.61; S, 17.43. C₇H₁₁N₃OS requires N, 22.70; S, 17.30%); 2b (R = C₆H₅; R' = H), m.p. 255° (lit.¹⁷ 257°); 2c (R = p-ClC₆H₄; R' = H), m.p. 275-76° (Found: N, 16.43; S, 12.76. C₁₀H₈ClN₃OS requires N, 16.57; S, 12.62%); 2d (R = p-MeOC₆H₄; R' = H), m.p. 254° (lit.¹⁷ 255°); 2e (R = OCHCHCHC-; R' = H),

Scheme 1

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m.p. 223-26° (lit.¹⁸ 223-24°); **2f** (R=n-C₆H₇; R'=Me), m.p. 175-77° (Found: N, 21.28; S, 16.23. C₈H₁₁S₂N₂O requires N, 21.11; S, 16.08%); **2g** (R=C₆H₅; R'=Me), m.p. 233° (lit.¹⁷ 231°); **2h** (R=p-ClC₆H₄; R'=Me), m.p. 198-99° (Found: N, 15.58; S, 11.79. C₁₁H₁₀ClN₂O requires N, 15.70; S, 11.96%); **2i** (R=p-MeOC₆H₄; R'=Me), m.p. 228° (lit.¹⁷ 229°); **2j** (R=OCHCHCHC-

ptoacetic acid (0.015 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h on water-bath. On cooling and stirring the reaction mixture, the desired precipitated product was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 1.

3-Alkyl/aryl-7-methyl (or unsubstituted)bis-thiazolo[3,4-b; 3',2'-d]-1,2,4-triazol-8(3H, 7H)-ones (4a-j): Compounds **3a-j** (0.01 mol) were treated dropwise with conc. H₂SO₄ (5 ml). The mixture was stirred under cooling for 0.5 h and then water added. On basification with aqueous ammonia the precipitated products were filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol to give **4a-j** (Table 1).

R'=Me), m.p. 202-3° (Found: N, 18.98; S, 14.22. C₉H₉N₃O₂S requires N, 18.83; S, 14.35%).

2-(2-Alkyl/aryl-4-oxothiazolidin-3-ylamino) - Δ²-thiazolin-4-ones (3a-j): To a well stirred solution of **2a-j** (0.01 mol) in dry benzene was added merca-

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF **3a-j** AND **4a-j**

Compd.	R	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)	
					N	S
R'=H						
3a	n-C ₆ H ₇	69	285-86	C ₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	16.92 (16.22)	24.61 (24.71)
3b	C ₆ H ₅	71	195	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	14.20 (14.38)	21.69 (21.84)
3c	p-ClC ₆ H ₄	68	290-81	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	12.67 (12.82)	19.81 (19.54)
3d	p-MeOC ₆ H ₄	72	237-88	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	13.25 (13.00)	19.69 (19.81)
3e	OCHCHCHC- 	75	210-19	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	14.73 (14.84)	22.82 (22.61)
R'=Me						
3f	n-C ₆ H ₇	65	208-11	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	15.45 (15.38)	23.12 (23.44)
3g	C ₆ H ₅	68	150-52	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	13.51 (13.68)	20.69 (20.85)
3h	p-ClC ₆ H ₄	63	191-93	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	12.23 (12.30)	18.91 (18.74)
3i	p-MeOC ₆ H ₄	67	162-63	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	12.81 (12.46)	19.18 (18.99)
3j	OCHCHCHC- 	71	199-202	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	12.27 (12.14)	21.39 (21.55)
R'=H						
4a	n-C ₆ H ₇	85	290-91	C ₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ OS ₂	17.56 (17.43)	26.41 (26.56)
4b	C ₆ H ₅	89	245	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ OS ₂	15.43 (15.27)	23.42 (23.27)
4c	p-ClC ₆ H ₄	87	287-88	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₂ OS ₂	13.39 (13.57)	20.51 (20.68)
4d	p-MeOC ₆ H ₄	92	256-53	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	13.51 (13.77)	20.69 (20.98)
4e	OCHCHCHC- 	95	224-26	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	15.98 (15.85)	24.01 (24.15)
R'=Me						
4f	n-C ₆ H ₇	73	221-22	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ OS ₂	16.65 (16.47)	24.97 (25.09)
4g	C ₆ H ₅	86	168-69	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ OS ₂	14.36 (14.53)	22.96 (23.15)
4h	p-ClC ₆ H ₄	85	201-2	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₂ OS ₂	12.81 (12.98)	19.89 (19.78)
4i	p-MeOC ₆ H ₄	90	178-79	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	12.99 (13.17)	19.91 (20.06)
4j	OCHCHCHC- 	94	210-12	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	15.21 (15.05)	22.73 (22.94)

Herbicidal screening : The herbicidal activity of 3a-j and 4a-j (Table 1) was evaluated by pre-emergence test against *Cyperus rotundus* and *Cynodon dactylon* at 1000, 100 and 10 ppm concentrations as described earlier⁴. A commercial herbicide, 2,4-D (sodium salt) was also tested under similar conditions for comparison.

Results and Discussion

All the screened compounds were considerably toxic to both the test weeds at 1000 ppm but their toxicity decreased markedly on dilution (at 10 ppm) except compounds 4c and 4h which exhibited the activity of the order of 2,4-D at 1000 ppm against both the test weeds and inhibited their germination to 40% even at 10 ppm. In general, the compounds 4a-j were more potent than their parent compounds 3a-j. The greater activity of these compounds might be attributed to their more planar structure than their parent compounds 3a-j. This presumption is in conformity with the earlier observations that compact size and planarity of a molecule often enhance its herbicidal activity¹³⁻¹⁵. It is noteworthy that the compounds 3c, 3h, 4c and 4h were more active than their analogues bearing some other substituent in the place of *p*-ClC₆H₄.

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References

1. D. CARTURIGHT and P. U. SMITH, Ger Pat. 2720792/1977 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, **88**, 62423).
2. O. WAKABAYASHI, K. MATSUTANI, K. OTA, T. JIKIHARA and S. SUZUKI, Jap. Pat. 7692586/1976 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, **85**, 94892).
3. H. SINGH, L. D. S. YADAV and B. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1977, **17**, 499.
4. B. K. BHATTACHARYA, H. SINGH, L. D. S. YADAV and G. HOORNAERT, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1982, **110**, 133.
5. Y. A. BASKAKOV, L. L. VOLOVNIK, A. F. VOSILER, N. L. ARYUTKINA and V. V. NEGREBETSKII, *Khim. Geterotsikl. Soedin.*, 1970, **11**, 1481 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1971, **74**, 53614).
6. J. KINUGAWA and E. MAGASE, Jap. Pat. 16285/1965 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1967, **66**, 10928).
7. C. K. BRADSHAW, F. O. BROWN and E. F. SINCLAIR, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **78**, 6189.
8. M. FISHMAN, U. S. Pat. 3796721/1974 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1974, **81**, 3918).
9. J. J. D'AMICO, U. S. Pat. 4185990/1980 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1980, **92**, 181168).
10. N. A. DAHLK, U. S. Pat. 4020678/1977 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, **87**, 39494).
11. L. NUSSLERIN and F. ARNDT, Ger. Pat. 2631647/1977 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, **88**, 105349).
12. S. KANO, E. TAKEUCHI and T. NOGUCHI, Jap. Pat. 7102655/1971 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1971, **74**, 141772).
13. L. A. SUMMERS, *Tetrahedron*, 1976, **32**, 615.
14. J. CHATT, L. A. DUNCANSON and L. M. VERNANZI, *Nature (London)*, 1956, **177**, 1042.
15. K. ROTHWELL and R. L. WAIN, *Ann. Appl. Biol.*, 1963, **51**, 161.
16. M. K. ROY and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 2427.
17. P. CHABRIER, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1947, 797 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1948, **42**, 2600).
18. P. CHABRIER and E. CALTELAIN, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1950, 46 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1951, **45**, 608).